

with ammonium thiocyanate afforded benzoyl thiocyanate which on treatment with aniline and substituted anilines gave a series of *N*-phenyl-*N'*-benzoylthioureas (1). Hydrolysis of these compounds with sodium hydroxide afforded the arylthioureas (2) in good yields³. Arylthioureas (2), when condensed with 5-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-2-bromoacetyl furan (4) gave the corresponding 2-arylamino-4-[(*p*-nitrophenyl)-2-furyl]thiazoles (5) in good yields. Similar condensation of 4 with thiourea afforded 2-amino-4-[5-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-2-furyl]thiazole (5a; R=H) (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 5*

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
5a	H	215	70	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃ S
5b	Phenyl	170	72	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃ S
5c	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	250	73	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ ClN ₃ O ₃ S
5d	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	255	70	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ ClN ₃ O ₃ S
5e	4-Dichlorophenyl	262	78	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₃ S
5f	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	223	75	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ S
5g	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	192	76	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ S
5h	3-Chloro-2-methylphenyl	218	75	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O ₃ S
5i	4-Chloro-2-methylphenyl	264	72	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O ₃ S
5j	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	204	70	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ BrN ₃ O ₃ S
5k	2-Pyridyl	283	74	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₃ S
5l	Morpholino	156	72	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ S

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Studies on Arylfuran Heterocycles. Part 2. Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of 2-Amino/2-Arylamino-4-[5-(*p*-nitro- phenyl)-2-furyl]thiazoles

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2-Aminothiazoles are important class of compounds possessing varied biological properties and their syntheses according to Hantzsch procedure have been extensively studied¹. In continuation of our work² on the synthesis and biological activities of arylfuran heterocycles, it was contemplated to synthesise arylfurfurylthiazoles carrying 2-amino/2-arylamino substituents and to screen them for their antibacterial activities.

The synthesis of 2-amino/2-arylamino-4-[5-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-2-furyl]thiazoles (5) was achieved as shown in Scheme 1. Reaction of benzoyl chloride

Scheme 1

The structures of the compounds (5) were confirmed by elemental analyses, ir, pmr and mass spectral data. The characteristic $\nu_{C=O}$ band of the starting material (4) was absent in the ir spectra of the condensed products. The ν_{NH} band of the condensed products (5) was seen as a broad band at 3 420–3 450 cm^{-1} , consistent with the stretching frequency of Ar-NH grouping. A band at 1 600–1 640 cm^{-1} of the condensed products suggests the presence of a thiazole ring. Characteristic asymmetric and symmetric stretching frequencies of the NO_2 group are manifested at 1 520 and 1 340 cm^{-1} respectively. The band at 1 110 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the C-S stretch of the thiazole ring.

The mass spectrum of compound 5a showed the expected molecular ion peak at m/z 287 consistent with the molecular formula C₁₃H₉N₃O₃S for this compound. The molecular ion peak was found to be the base peak and there were few fragment peaks in the mass spectrum of 5a indicating the presence of a stable 2-aminothiazole nucleus in the condensed product. The molecular ion underwent two modes of fragmentation, namely, $M-\text{NO}$ and $M-\text{NO}_2$, characteristic of aromatic NO_2 compounds⁴. A peak at m/z 257 was attributed to the ion obtained by the loss of NO radical from the molecular ion, while a peak at m/z 241 is attributed to an ion obtained by the loss of NO_2 radical from the molecular ion. It is important to note that no fragmentation of the aminothiazole ring was observed. The mass spectrum of 5g was also recorded. The molecular ion peak in conformity with

the molecular formula $C_{20}H_{15}N_3O_3S$ was observed at m/z 377; it was also found to be the base peak. Two fragment peaks were detected at m/z 347 and 331 which correspond to the ions obtained by the loss of NO and NO_2 radicals respectively from the molecular ion.

Further evidence in support of the assigned structure for the condensation products (5) was obtained from the pmr spectra of two compounds of this series. Most of the condensation products had poor solubility in common solvents used in pmr spectroscopy. Pmr spectra of 5g showed a broad hump at δ 10.01 which could be assigned to the NH proton of the arylamino moiety while signals of the aromatic and furan rings merged together and appeared as a complex multiplet at δ 6.8–8.0. A doublet (J 8.0 Hz) appearing at δ 8.15 integrating for two protons could be attributed to the aromatic protons adjacent to the NO_2 group. A singlet at δ 7.05 in the spectrum of 5g characteristic⁵ of thiazole 5-H further confirmed the formation of the thiazole ring. The methyl protons of the aromatic ring were found at δ 2.2. Pmr spectrum of 5a was consistent with the assigned structure. The aromatic protons of the phenyl moiety resonated as two doublets (J 8.8 Hz) at δ 8.37 and 8.19 while the two β -protons of the furyl moiety⁶ appeared as two doublets (J 3.8 Hz) at δ 7.96 and 7.63. The thiazole proton signal appeared as a sharp singlet at δ 7.61 consistent with the structure.

Some selected compounds were screened for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against *S. typhi*, *S. aureus*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* at 20 μ g ml^{-1} concentration using cup-plate diffusion method. Compound 5c showed promising activity against all bacteria except *P. aeruginosa*.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol or KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (DMSO- d_6) either on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) or a Bruker WH-200 (270 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS D-300 spectrometer operating at 70 eV.

N-Substituted-arylthioureas used in the present investigation were prepared according to reported methods and characterised³.

5-(*p*-Nitrophenyl)-2-bromoacetylfuran (4): To 5-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-2-acetylfuran⁷ (0.1 mol) dissolved in dioxane (150 ml), a solution of bromine in acetic acid (30% w/v, 50 ml) was added dropwise with stirring during 1 h. The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 3 h, concentrated to half its volume under reduced pressure and cooled. The resulting solid was recrystallised from aqueous DMF as yellow needles (70%), m.p. 145° (Found: C, 46.68; H, 2.89; N, 4.84. $C_{12}H_8BrNO_4$ calcd. for: C, 46.45; H, 2.58; N, 4.51%).

2-Arylamino-4-[5-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-2-furyl]thiazoles (5). *General procedure:* An equimolecular mixture of appropriate *N*-arylthiourea (2; 10 mmol) and 5-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-2-bromoacetylfuran (4) was heated on a steam-bath for 6 h. It was then cooled to room temperature and diluted with ice-cold water. The resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from DMF or a mixture of DMF-alcohol to yield the title compounds (Table 1).

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